

**PSYCHOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL AND PHYSICAL ASPECTS OF
PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS**

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Anatisation: Ways to develop mental, psychological and pedagogical abilities of primary school students through chess. Through this, the superiority of the game of chess was revealed to the intellectual abilities of young people.

Key words. Children of preschool age, Game activities, personal characteristics, psychological, social and physical development, chess, mental ability.

Primary school age is determined by a very important external situation that occurs in a child's life - he enters school. The transition from preschool childhood to school life is one of the turning points in a person's mental and, naturally, personal development. By the age of six or seven, in a certain sense, the child can already express himself as a person and understand what place he occupies among people as a preschooler and what place he will occupy when he goes to school. The child somehow needs to go beyond the limits of his childish behavior, occupy a new place available to him and engage in more serious activities. The transition from play activity to learning is taking place, which will now be the leader for the child. And this activity makes completely new demands on it compared to the game.

Enrollment in school changes the most important changes in a child's life, the whole way of life, social status, position in the community and family. From now on, teaching becomes the leading activity of a first grade student, the most important task is the obligation to study and acquire knowledge. People around now perceive the child as a person who has certain obligations to learn, which are typical for all children of this age. Teaching is a serious job that requires certain organization, discipline and certain willpower. More and more often, you should do what you need, not what you want. According to H. Heibsch and J. Lompsher, teaching is not only an activity aimed at acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities, but also a process of forming personal characteristics, and in the concept of "teaching" the main focus is on the mental results of the activity (subjective changes, formation and improvement of personal qualities).

Currently, educational activity is becoming a leading activity in a child's life, because it not only occupies an important place in time, but also the development of the student's personality, although not only, but mainly occurs

in specific educational activities. "Educational activity at school age is the leading one, because, firstly, the child's main relations with society are realized through it; secondly, it consists of the formation of both the main personal characteristics and individual mental processes of a school-aged child.

The beginning of schooling is one of the most difficult psychological, social and physical periods in a child's life. The whole life of the child changes - new relationships, new living conditions, a completely new type of activity, new requirements, etc. It is on the basis of educational activities that the main psychological neoplasms develop in young schoolchildren. Education pushes thinking to the center of the child's mind and becomes the dominant function, it begins to determine work and all other functions of the mind - they become individualized and arbitrary.

Since studying at school is singled out as a leading activity, the psychological characteristics of primary school age are determined accordingly. Reconstruction of cognitive processes means the formation of arbitrariness, productivity and stability - the development of voluntary attention, perception, memory (primarily mechanical memory), thinking moves from visual-figurative to verbal-logical at the level of concrete concepts; self-regulation of behavior and will; the skills of reading, writing, arithmetic calculation are mastered and improved, knowledge is accumulated.

It was considered above that primary school students are in the period of mental and psychological development.

Therefore, good development of young people of this age is considered desirable.

It is precisely our use of chess in the development of the child's mental abilities that we expect. Because the sport of chess is the most effective way to develop a person's mental abilities. It is not for nothing that the German writer I. Goethe said, "Chess is the ingot of the mind." Many such tariffs can be cited as an example. Chess teaches to act rationally, to feel responsible, to strive to increase knowledge, to think independently. It is necessary for everyone. (Dutch chess player. Max E).

We can see that great chess players and mature thinkers also put forward their ideas that chess can develop human mental abilities. Therefore, the wide use of the chess game in the development of the child's mental abilities will give the expected effect.

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